

MANAGEMENT SUPERVISION OF MADRASAH HEADS IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF THE LEARNING PROCESS (RESEARCH AT MTS YPP DARUL HIKAM AND MTS AL-FALAH BANJARAN BANDUNG)

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Abstract

The role of supervision of the head of the madrasah which has an impact on weak learning outcomes and low teacher performance in both schools. In general, this study is to prove that the supervision carried out by the Head of Madrasah can improve the quality of the learning process at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al Falah Banjaran Bandung Regency. The specific objectives are to know and obtain an overview and understanding of: 1) Planning, 2) Organizing, 3) Implementation, 4) Supervision, 5) Constraints, 6) Supervision management solutions for madrasah heads in improving the quality of the learning process and 7) Quality of the learning process at MTS YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung Regency. This research is a descriptive qualitative research that aims to make a systematic, factual and accurate picture of the facts, phenomena investigated related to the supervision management of the head of the madrasah in improving the quality of the learning process. This research data was obtained through observation, interviews and documentation. All collected data is then analyzed using data analysis consisting of data reduction stages, data presentation, and verification.

Keywords: Management Supervision, Quality of The Learning Process.

INTRODUCTION

Education plays an important role in determining the quality of human resources. In essence, the quality of a nation and state is not only characterized by its beauty and natural wealth, but most importantly lies in the superiority of human resources. The excellence of human resources is closely related to the quality of education. The quality of education is often characterized by good conditions and qualifications in all components of education which include processes, outputs, educational personnel, infrastructure and costs. Meanwhile, the quality of education cannot be separated from the education and teaching process that takes place in an educational institution that demands systematic and planned coordination efforts.

Education not only equips intelligence, but also competence and ethical values as well as character formation that makes students have a strong identity and trust in their competence (Pupuh and Suryana, 2011: 3). School is not only a process related to knowledge, but also includes several things related to physical, emotional, and financial aspects in realizing the vision and mission. This method is a systematic effort and continuously improves service quality, so that the focus is directed to customers, in this case students, parents of students, graduate users, teachers, government and employees. There are at least five services that must

be owned, namely, services in accordance with what is promised (reliability), able to guarantee learning (assurance), a conducive school climate (tangible), giving full attention to students (empathetic), and quickly responding to the needs of students (responsiveness) (Mulyasa, 2013: 26).

Improving the quality of education is a task that is not easy because it is influenced by various factors such as the quality of educational input, the quality of educational resources, the quality of teachers and education managers, the quality of the learning process, the ability of education managers to anticipate and handle various influences of the educational environment. In terms of education, according to the opinion of Sergiovani and Starrat quoted by E. Mulyasa (2006: 111)

A school can be a successful institution if its principal, teachers and employees are able to carry out the functions and practices of good education governance or management. The level of quality of human resources is highly dependent on the educational process, both formal and informal approaches.

A country, be it a developed or newly developing country, prioritizes the need for educational services. The progress of a country is certainly inseparable from the existence of educated and skilled humans. Likewise, Indonesia is a developing country and is actively implementing development, be it development in the physical or non-physical fields, including development in the field of education.

Supervision as an activity designed to improve teaching at all levels of schooling, related to the development and growth of children, supervision is also an aid in the development of good teaching and learning. So, the main task of supervision is to help teachers gain direction and solve their own teaching problems. Supervision is a set of activities and role formulations specifically designed to influence teaching to be carried out more qualified. Supervision of education is focused on improving teaching as an effort to grow the professional position of teachers, emphasis given to the integration of individual needs with the educational objectives of the main tasks in madrasahs.

The supervisor is in charge of providing guidance and counseling, for the progress of the madrasah. Therefore, those in charge of being supervisors must be generous or wise in accepting various suggestions and criticisms from all parties so that every decision making produces something that is best for the progress of the madrasah. Madrasah teachers and employees are relentlessly directed and nurtured and guided to achieve perfection in their work. The head of the madrasah must also have high knowledge and skills in accordance with his area of responsibility in the madrasah. The head of the madrasah must also have creative ideas that can improve the development of the madrasah.

The task of a supervisor is to help, encourage and give confidence to teachers, that the teaching and learning process can provide the development of various experiences, knowledge, attitudes and skills of teachers, and the learning process carried out by the teacher must be assisted professionally so that teachers can develop in their work, namely to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the teaching and learning process. Improving the performance of teachers in

carrying out their noble duties is the responsibility of the head of the madrasah to teachers and students in the madrasah. Motivational assistance can be in the form of rewarding outstanding teachers, providing coaching in effective and fun learning methods, and also giving strict punishment as good education to teachers who do not carry out their duties well as logical consequences.

Competencies that must be possessed by a madrasah head, one of which is a competency that is difficult to implement is supervision competence. Supervision activities for teachers for madrasah heads are a burden of duty, while for teachers supervision is a matter to assess and find fault with teachers in teaching in class. The head of the madrasah does not have the knowledge and skills to carry out academic supervision of his teachers. This needs special attention from the direct supervisor of the head of the madrasah, namely the supervisor of the madrasah or the authorities in an effort to increase the competence of the head of the madrasah which is more incentive in the future to have knowledge, skills, abilities and confidence in carrying out duties as a supervisor in the madrasah.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used is qualitative descriptive method. In this study, researchers conducted interviews with a number of informants who had been determined, because the competencies they had were in accordance with the object of research to be analyzed. This research was conducted to find out about "Management Supervision of the Head of Madrasah in improving the quality of the teaching and learning process". In this study, the method used is the Descriptive Analytical research method. Descriptive Analytical Method is a research intended to collect information about the status of an existing symptom, namely symptoms according to what they are at the time the study is carried out regardless of before and after by processing, analyzing, interpreting, and concluding research data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Head of MTs YPP Darul Hikam Bandung carried out several stages of supervision activities to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process he set in the field of supervision in madrasahs. Before supervision activities are carried out. The head of the madrasah conducts planning activities in the form of formulating a supervision program by involving small meetings with several senior teachers and deputy heads of the madrasah. The first step taken was to form a Supervision Assistant Team which was given a Decree (SK) by the Head of the madrasah.

The supervision assistant team that has been formed is planned to assist the head of the madrasah in carrying out the supervision duties carried out with the aim of streamlining supervision activities in the madrasah. The members of the Supervision Auxiliary Team are senior teachers with a rank above the supervised teachers and are considered capable or capable by the head of the madrasah to carry out their supervision duties properly and impartially,

meaning able to assess what is really happening. Through observations and document findings, the Supervision Assistant Team and the head of the madrasah have a comprehensive picture of the actual condition of the teaching and learning process. The results of careful observation and documentation findings form the basis for evaluating the successful implementation of previous supervision programs and for formulating corrective steps going forward.

The interview with the deputy head of the madrasah added an important dimension to the supervision program, namely attention to the study schedule and academic calendar at the beginning of the semester. The supervision program developed with the Supervision Assistant Team includes short, medium, and long-term programs, and is designed to overcome teacher difficulties in the learning process. The active involvement of the Supervision Assistant Team in the preparation of this program shows strong collaboration between madrasah heads and senior teachers in dealing with the dynamics of learning activities.

By digging deeper into the results of observations and document findings, madrasah can identify strengths and weaknesses of previous supervision implementation. These findings provide a concrete basis for formulating improvement strategies that are more targeted and responsive to the needs of madrasahs. Thus, the results of observation and document analysis are not only an evaluation tool, but also a guideline for achieving the learning quality goals that have been set.

The results of this in-depth observation were obtained through valuable contributions from three main informant sources, namely supervisors, madrasah heads, and teachers at MTs YPP Darul Hikam Bandung.

First of all, supervisors play an important role in providing an external perspective on the implementation of supervision activities in madrasahs. Supervisors have broad insight into education policies, teaching and learning standards, and best practices in madrasah management. Observations made by supervisors provide an independent assessment of the effectiveness of the supervision program, ensure that teaching and learning standards are met, and provide constructive feedback for further improvement.

The head of the madrasah, as the main leader in the implementation of supervision, provides deep insight into the strategy of planning and implementing the supervision program. The observations illustrate the seriousness of the head of the madrasah in involving the Supervision Assistance Team, formulating class visit schedules, and implementing a standard process supervision format. In addition, through interviews with the head of the madrasah, information was obtained about the vision and mission of the madrasah which became the basis for formulating short, medium and long term supervision program targets.

Furthermore, the perspective of the teacher as a direct actor in the teaching and learning process is invaluable in describing the impact of the supervision program. Observations of teachers show how they accept and respond to supervision, as well as the extent to which they find it helpful to overcome learning problems. Interviews with teachers provide insight into the role of the Supervision Assistance Team in helping them structure the supervision program and how it can provide concrete solutions to the challenges faced in day-to-day teaching.

Supervision planning at MTs YPP Darul Hikam, Bandung, describes a mature process and involves collaboration between the head of the madrasah, senior teachers, and deputy heads of the madrasah. Based on the results of the study which included interviews with Supervisors, Madrasah Heads, and Teachers, direct observation of supervision activities, and analysis of related documents, a more detailed interview narrative can be drawn.

Supervision planning at MTs YPP Darul Hikam, Bandung, is seen as an organized process and involves active participation from various parties, such as madrasah heads, senior teachers, and deputy madrasah heads. An interview with the head of the madrasah, H. Muzhoffar, conducted on Tuesday, November 1, 2018, provided insight into the planning stages involving small meetings with senior teachers and deputy heads of the madrasa. These interviews create a formal and serious atmospheric picture, highlighting the role of madrasah heads as leaders who listen and facilitate discussions.

The results of observation and document analysis show the active involvement of the Supervision Assistance Team in supporting the success of supervision planning. The team not only monitors learning activities, but also provides constructive input to supervised teachers. In addition, supervision outcome documents include lesson plans, evaluation results, and student progress records, all of which form the basis for the formulation of short, medium, and long-term supervision program goals.

In the third phase of this study, researchers explored the results of supervision and document analysis that reflected the effectiveness of the program at MTs YPP Darul Hikam. Superintendents, madrasah heads, and teachers are the main sources of information to present a complete picture of the impact and achievement of supervision.

Observations during the implementation of supervision illustrate that the Supervision Assistance Team is very active and has a significant role in supporting the success of the program. The supervisor can provide a rich perspective through his or her observations of classroom interactions. Interviews with members of the supervision team highlight their awareness of the importance of providing constructive feedback and implementable solutions.

In the end, the results of this study reflect the serious efforts made by MTs YPP Darul Hikam Bandung in improving the quality of the learning process through organizing the supervision of the head of the madrasah. Although several obstacles were identified, such as discipline, complex situations and conditions, limited facilities and funds, and mental attitudes that have not been fully supported, the efforts and initiatives of the head of the madrasah are clearly visible. The importance of discipline and better coordination among teaching staff is a focus of potential improvement, while improving facilities and infrastructure through better allocation of funds can have a positive impact on the quality of learning. The proactive attitude of the head of the madrasah in providing coaching and training to teachers shows a commitment to professional development and improving the quality of learning.

This research provides a deeper understanding of the reality on the ground and can be the foundation for MTs YPP Darul Hikam Bandung to develop more effective strategies and policies to improve the quality of the learning process in the future. By continuing to improve

the obstacles identified, it is hoped that schools can achieve higher learning standards and have a positive impact on student achievement,

Based on the results of observations and document analysis at MTs Darul Hikam Bandung, it seems that there are several inhibiting factors in the implementation of supervision that require concrete solutions to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process. The results of interviews with madrasah heads, waka curricula, and teachers, as well as examination of related documents, revealed several solutions that could be implemented.

First, the head of the madrasah acts as a supervisor who monitors, fosters, and improves the teaching and learning process in the classroom or in the madrasah. The first solution is to ensure that supervision of the implementation of teaching and learning activities is carried out consistently and continuously. Principles such as consultative, collegial, and democratic relationships form the basis for the implementation of supervision. Second, group discussions are often held as a form of cooperation between teachers and madrasah heads in solving problems and reaching mutual decisions. The second solution is to strengthen the practice of group discussions as a means to solve problems and increase cooperation among madrasah staff. Third, class visits were identified as an effective technique for observing learning activities directly. The third solution is to maintain and improve the effectiveness of class visits as a tool to observe and provide immediate feedback regarding classroom learning. Fourth, individual talk is recognized as a guidance and counseling technique that can be used by madrasah heads to provide support to teachers personally. The fourth solution is to maintain and improve the practice of individual speaking as a form of personal support and guidance. Fifth, learning simulation, although not described in detail in the document, is recognized as a technique in the form of learning demonstrations that can provide a direct picture to teachers. The fifth solution is to further clarify and integrate the practice of simulating learning as an effort to increase teacher understanding of effective learning methods and strategies.

The commitment of the head of the madrasah in providing coaching to teachers is a key point in the supervision process. Interviews show that the head of the madrasah is proactively involved in providing direction, motivation, and guidance to teachers within his madrasah. Group discussion is one form of interaction used to discuss factors that may be obstacles, especially related to teacher education background that is not always in accordance with the field of study of the head of the madrasah. Individual coaching is also an approach used to ensure that each teacher can develop professionally, in line with the vision and mission of madrasah education.

Direct observation of teaching and learning activities shows the concrete implementation of supervision carried out by the head of the madrasah. Monitoring teacher and student discipline, time management, and the use of teaching methods are the main focus. Picket teachers who are activated to maintain the smooth teaching and learning process are concrete examples of the efforts of madrasah heads in creating an orderly and conducive learning environment.

The supervised document records the follow-up given to teachers who need improvement in aspects of discipline or teaching performance. These actions include the development of

improvement plans and regular monitoring. With this approach, supervision management serves not only as an evaluation tool, but also as a means of teacher professional development. The strategy of sending teachers to participate in various professional development activities, such as workshops, upgrades, and training, is a manifestation of the efforts of the head of the madrasah to improve the quality of human resources in the madrasah environment. The observation data and documentation of the training that the teachers participated in reflected their active participation and involvement in the process of self-development.

The problem that arises related to the supervision of the head of the madrasah at MTs Al-Falah Banjaran is the mismatch of the teacher's field of study with the educational background of the head of the madrasah. Observations show that this situation can be a significant obstacle, especially when the head of a madrasa must involve himself in academic supervision. From the results of an interview conducted on November 25, 2018, the head of the madrasah conveyed his difficulty in carrying out academic supervision for teachers who have fields of study that are not in line with their educational background. Observations suggest that these differences may affect the effectiveness of communication and understanding between madrasah heads and teachers, given the complexity of understanding the specific nuances and needs of different fields of study.

The document on the results of teacher supervision and performance evaluation also shows that some teachers who have fields of study that are not in line with the background of the head of the madrasah experience challenges in understanding the direction and input given. This complicates the process of developing and improving the quality of learning, since effective supervision requires a deep understanding of the specific field of study being supervised. Thus, from the results of observation and analysis of documents, it appears that this difficulty can hinder the effectiveness of supervision and requires a more appropriate approach strategy to overcome this challenge. Improvement efforts must be made so that supervision continues to have a positive impact on improving the quality of the learning process at MTs Al-Falah Banjaran.

Observation and analysis of documents at MTs Al-Falah Banjaran show that one of the inhibiting factors in the implementation of supervision is sudden busy work, especially when the head of the madrasa has to attend an official meeting that cannot be abandoned. This finding is supported by data recorded in various documents, such as daily activity schedules and activity reports of madrasah heads. Field observations showed that there were several changes in the schedule of pre-planned academic supervision activities. This can be a serious obstacle in achieving well-scheduled supervision goals. Meeting notes and activity agendas of madrasah heads also reflect a sometimes sudden shift in work priorities, which then affects the availability of time for supervision.

From the results of this analysis, it can be seen that the factor of sudden busyness of the head of the madrasah is one of the main obstacles in the implementation of supervision. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct more careful evaluation and planning in preparing the supervision schedule, as well as considering work priorities that may affect the implementation of academic supervision at MTs Al-Falah Banjaran.

In an effort to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process at MTs Al Falah Bandung, the head of the madrasah tried to overcome several supervision obstacles by providing concrete solutions. First, the head of the madrasah realizes the importance of motivating teachers as an effort to empower and develop professionalism. Observations of supervision activities show that madrasah heads routinely motivate teachers, accommodating their individual characteristics and needs. The inspected documents also reflect the motivation programs implemented, such as training and workshops to improve teacher performance.

Second, through discussion activities, the head of the madrasah creates a forum for dialogue and finding joint solutions to the obstacles faced by teachers with different educational backgrounds. Observations stated that the discussion led to a common understanding and the formation of concrete solutions related to differences in teacher education backgrounds. The discussion documents record notes on strategies and measures to improve cooperation among teachers. Third, in response to the busy head of the madrasah that hinders the implementation of supervision according to schedule, the head of the madrasah creates a solution to delegate the implementation of supervision to the deputy head of the madrasah or the Supervision Assistant Team. Observation and examination of documents show that the Supervision Assistant Team has been actively involved in carrying out academic supervision, providing feedback, and recording emerging findings. The document records the results of the team's supervision, showing the positive impact of task delegation. Thus, these solutions are expected to help MTs Al Falah Bandung in optimizing the implementation of supervision, creating sustainable motivation, increasing cooperation between teachers, and ensuring the smooth implementation of supervision even in the busy situation of the head of the madrasah

Based on the previous discussion about the management of supervision of the head of the madrasah at MTs Al-Falah Banjaran, it can be explained that the impact of the supervision is seen in improving the quality of learning in the madrasah. Interviews, observations, and documents support this understanding.

In an interview with the head of the madrasah, he emphasized the importance of supervision as an effort to improve teacher performance and the quality of learning. The head of the madrasah actively provides coaching to teachers, both directly and through various activities such as group discussions, class visits, individual talks, and learning simulations. This is reflected in the statement of the head of the madrasah, "I try to help teachers according to my ability, either directly or based on existing theories. The teacher feels more accepting, I sometimes express what I am if there is something not right, so that there is no grundel behind."

The observations also reflect the positive contribution of supervision to the quality of learning. Workshops, upgrades, and training activities attended by teachers as a result of supervision, provide space for them to improve their insights, skills, and learning methods. For example, sending teachers to attend various education and training at the cluster or sub-district level regularly, subject teacher deliberation (MGMP), and workshop seminar discussions are recognized as effective means of developing teacher competence.

The context of supervision of teachers is also evident from the application of various supervision techniques, such as class visits, group discussions, and individual talks. The use of these various techniques allows madrasah heads to understand the needs and challenges of each teacher more deeply, so that the guidance provided can be more directed and useful. Documents related to supervision and teacher participation in professional development activities provide a solid foundation to prove the effectiveness of the supervision management of madrasah heads. These data reflect the commitment and seriousness of madrasah in achieving the goal of quality education. Thus, the supervision management of the head of the madrasah at MTs Al-Falah Banjaran is not only limited to fulfilling administrative formalities, but is actually reflected in improving the quality of learning, teacher coaching, and the overall learning environment. The continuity of this effort is the foundation to have a sustainable positive impact on the quality of education in the madrasah.

Discussion

One of the duties of the head of the madrasah is to carry out supervision. The implementation of supervision by the head of the madrasah is important in improving the quality of the principal. Supervision activities are assistance or guidance from teachers to be more professional in organizing learning for their students. In the implementation of supervision, the head of the madrasah not only assesses the appearance of the teacher in managing the learning process, but rather coaches teachers to improve their professionalism, which will later have an impact on improving the quality of learning. This is in line with the understanding of supervision according to Nur Aedi (2014: 183) which emphasizes that the essence of supervision is not to measure or assess the performance of teachers but as an effort to help teachers develop their professional capabilities.

1. Planning Supervision of the Head of Madrasah to Improve the Quality of the Teaching and Learning Process

Before the supervision activities of the head of the madrasah to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process were carried out, the head of the madrasah carried out activities in the field of planning in the form of formulating a supervision program by involving a small meeting with several senior teachers and deputy heads of the madrasah. In the framework of school management, planning means that the principal and his team think about setting the targets of the previous activities. Activities are based more on methods, logical thinking, and analysis than on preconceived notions. Long-term planning requires balance. The plan provides a target direction for the organization and reflects the best procedures (Danim, Suparno, 2009: 9).

By looking at the explanation above, the first step taken by the two schools, both MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung, was to form a Supervision Assistant Team which was given a Decree (SK) by the Head of Madrasah. The supervision assistant team that has been formed is planned to assist the head of the madrasah in carrying out the supervision duties carried out with the aim of streamlining supervision activities in the madrasah. The members of the Supervision Auxiliary Team are senior teachers with a rank above the

supervised teachers and are considered capable or capable by the head of the madrasah to carry out their supervision duties properly and impartially, meaning that they are able to assess what is really happening. Supervision program planning is based on teacher needs or madrasah needs. This is in line with the opinion of Sergiovanni and Daresh, (in <http://id.shvoong.com/social-sciences/education/2025213-supervision-academic/>), which states that the level of ability, need, interest, and professional maturity and other personal characteristics of teachers should be used as a basis for planning considerations in developing and implementing supervision programs. Management as a collectivity is a collection of people who work together to achieve a common goal. This collectivity or collection of people is called management, while people who are responsible for the implementation of a goal or the running of management activities are called managers. From the definition above, it can be concluded that management is the coordination of all resources through the process of planning, organizing, determining manpower, directing and supervising to achieve the goals that have been set first. Management in the discussion of this research is teacher recruitment management, which is a series of resource coordination through the process of planning, organizing, directing and supervising in recruiting teachers.

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2. Organizing Supervision of the Head of Madrasah to Improve the Quality of the Learning Process

Organizing is an arrangement, procedure, work procedure, governance, and others that regulate the organization so that it can run smoothly. Organizing is a process of organizing and allocating work, authority, and resources within organizational members, so as to achieve organizational goals efficiently (Danim, Suparno, 2009: 9). Organizing is a joint effort by a group of people to achieve the goals that have been set before by utilizing existing resources in order to achieve effective and efficient results (Arikunto, Lia Yuliana, 2013: 9).

Based on the above understanding, organizing determines the capabilities of the type of program needed and organizes all the potential possessed to achieve predetermined goals. This function is intended so that members of the school organization or teaching staff can work on ways that will help achieve the goals that have been set. Organizing can be achieved with good work procedures, then an organization has the following principles: (1) have clear goals that are understood and accepted by all members so that in the organization there is only one unity of direction. Goals like this are usually called vision, derived from English vision, which is the result to be aspired to, (2) has an organizational structure that describes the existence of one command, a balance of tasks, authority and responsibilities that facilitate the path and not too

many people involved in the responsibility (Arikunto, Lia Yuliana, 2013: 10).

In accordance with its function, supervision must be able to coordinate all efforts in the madrasah environment which can include the efforts of each teacher in self-actualization and participate in improving madrasah activities. Thus, it needs to be coordinated in a directed manner so that it can really support the smooth running of the overall program. Overall, the organization of supervision of madrasah heads at MTs Darul Hikam Bandung and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran reflects a commitment in creating an optimal learning environment. Through these various strategies, madrasah heads strive to improve the quality of teachers and the learning process as a whole, with the main aim of achieving a better quality of learning.

3. Implementation of Supervision of the Head of Madrasah to Improve the Quality of the Teaching and Learning Process

The implementation of supervision at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung is always monitored or monitored by the head of the madrasah, then the results are evaluated. Before the supervision activity begins, the head of the madrasah conducts pre-class visit activities in the form of interviews and checks the completeness of learning tools that will be used by the teacher. The head of the madrasah also followed up by holding post-supervision activities to reflect on the results of the supervision that had been carried out. The form of follow-up carried out is in the form of sharing and then listening to the explanation of the teacher concerned. This activity is intended to know and identify various difficulties and the goodness or strength of the teacher during the learning process.

Supervision is an activity carried out by supervisors of education units in order to assist principals, teachers and other education personnel to improve the quality and effectiveness of education and learning implementation. Supervision is aimed at two aspects, namely managerial and academic. Managerial supervision focuses on observing aspects of school management and administration that function as support for the implementation of learning. While academic supervision focuses on supervisory observations of academic activities, in the form of learning both inside and outside the classroom. The hadith of the Holy Prophetsa also advocated the need to carry out supervision or evaluation in every work. Islamic teachings are very concerned about the form of self-supervision first before supervising others.

4. Supervision of Management Supervision of the Head of Madrasah in Improving the Quality of the Learning Process

Supervision and control carried out by the principal is not only focused on education personnel, especially teachers, it can be non-education personnel, or other school staff. Because supervision has a very important function, especially for teachers who aim to improve professional abilities and improve the quality of learning, because teachers are the spearhead of the implementation of Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM), and this has a direct effect on the educational process which ultimately has an impact on the quality of education quality. The principal's duties as a supervisor are manifested in his ability to compile and implement educational supervision programs and utilize the results. The ability to compile an educational supervision program must be realized in the preparation of class supervision programs, the

development of supervision programs for extra-curricular activities, the development of library supervision programs, laboratories and examinations. The ability to carry out educational supervision programs is manifested in the implementation of clinical supervision programs and in extra-curricular activity supervision programs. While the ability to utilize the results of educational supervision is manifested in the use of supervision results to improve the performance of education personnel and the use of supervision results to develop schools. Semantically Supervision of education is coaching towards improving the educational situation. The guidance in question is in the form of guidance or guidance towards improving the educational situation, including teaching in general and improving the quality of teaching and learning in particular. According to Sudjana in Yoseptry, et al (2022). states that academic supervision is a series of activities to help teachers develop their abilities in managing the learning process in order to achieve learning goals. Academic supervision is an effort to help teachers develop their abilities to achieve learning goals (Daresh, 1989). Sudjana said that academic supervision is assessing and developing teachers in order to improve the quality of the learning process in order to obtain more optimal student learning outcomes.

5. Obstacles that Occur in the Supervision of the Head of Madrasah to Improve the Quality of the Teaching and Learning Process

In essence, educational supervision can be interpreted as professional guidance for teachers. Professional guidance in question is all matters that provide opportunities for teachers to develop professionally, so that they are more advanced in carrying out their main task, which is to improve and improve the learning process of students. Supervision is a process, which is a series of activities to bring teachers to a higher level of ability. Supervision cannot be completed by one activity in the form of class visits alone or only by conducting interviews or having teachers attend upgrades (UPI Education Administration Lecturer Team: 2014, 318).

The Head of Madrasah as a supervisor has the role and responsibility of monitoring, fostering, and improving the teaching and learning process in the classroom or in the madrasah (Prim Masrokan: 2013, 246). In relation to supervision, that the main activity in madrasah in order to realize educational goals is learning activities, so that all madrasah organizational activities lead to achieving learning efficiency and effectiveness. Therefore, one of the roles and duties of madrasah is as a supervisor (supervising), namely supervising the work carried out by education personnel, in this case teachers. Mulyasa (2004: 21) said that supervision is an effort to observe systematically and continuously, record, provide explanations, instructions, coaching and rectifying various things that are not right, and correct mistakes.

6. Solutions in Overcoming the Supervision of Madrasah Heads to Improve the Quality of the Teaching and Learning Process

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on the educational process which ultimately has an impact on the quality of education.

So what is meant by the quality of education is the quality of teachers, both their understanding or their ability to interact with teaching and learning whose indicators can be seen from student learning achievement, be it achievement in taking semester exams or achievement in taking final exams. Understanding quality is the superiority of a product in the form of goods and services, which satisfies and meets customer desires and customer needs. In the context of education, the notion of quality in this case refers to the educational process and educational outcomes (Sallis, 2006: 56).

Because Education is a major factor in the formation of the human person. Education plays a role in shaping the good or bad of the human person according to normative measures. Realizing this, the government is very serious about handling the field of education, because with a good education system, it is hoped that the next generation of the nation will emerge who are qualified and able to adapt to life in society, nation and state.

The solutions in overcoming the supervision of the Head of Madrasah to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung, namely: Supervision of the Implementation of Teaching and Learning Activities, group discussions, class visits, individual talks, learning simulations, Motivating teachers, Delegation of Supervision Implementation, discussion, and Delegation of Supervision Implementation. This is in accordance with previous research conducted by Kamarudin in his 2008 thesis, entitled *The Relationship between School Culture and Integrated Quality Management with Job Satisfaction of Tsanawiyah Madrasah Teachers in Pontianak City*. The results of this study show 1) there is a positive relationship between school culture and job satisfaction of teachers of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Kota Pontianak, 2) there is a positive relationship between integrated quality management and job satisfaction of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Kota Pontianak teachers, 3) there is a positive relationship between school culture and integrated quality management together with job satisfaction of Madrasah Tsanawiyah teachers Pontianak City.

7. Quality of the Learning Process at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung Regency

The quality of learning at MTs Darul Hikam Bandung and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran is reflected through a number of aspects involving the supervision management of the head of the madrasah. The results of interviews, observations, and document analysis provide an overview of concrete efforts taken by madrasah heads to improve the quality of the learning process.

Delegation of supervision implementation is also a smart solution in overcoming obstacles to the busyness of madrasah heads. The deputy head of the madrasah or the Supervision Assistant Team of the Head of the Madrasah plays an active role in carrying out the task of supervision, as revealed by the head of the MTs Darul Hikam Bandung madrasah. By involving the team, the head of the madrasah can still ensure that the implementation of supervision runs smoothly even though it has a busy schedule.

Overall, the quality of learning at MTs Darul Hikam Bandung and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran can be measured by the extent to which the policies and strategies of supervision management of madrasah heads can respond to the needs and challenges faced by teachers. Coordinated and sustained efforts to provide motivation, increase teacher engagement, and provide infrastructure support, help create an optimal learning environment to achieve the expected quality of learning.

Learning is a process carried out by providing education and training to students to achieve learning outcomes. Changes as a result of the learning process can be proposed in various forms such as changes in knowledge, understanding, attitudes and behavior, skills, abilities and abilities, reaction power, acceptability and other aspects that exist in individuals who learn (Sudjana, 2000).

Learning is anything that can bring information and knowledge in the interaction that takes place between educators and students. (Asyar, 2011). Learning according to psychological understanding is a process of behavior change as a result of interaction with the environment in determining the needs of life. These changes will be evident in all aspects of behavior.

According to classical psychology, the essence of learning is that all learning is a process of developing or training of mind. Learning is seeing objects using substance and sensation. According to the mental state theory, learning is acquiring knowledge through the senses conveyed in the form of external stimulants. Experiences of association and reproduction. Therefore, training plays an important role.

The importance of providing motivation to teachers, both through group discussions, individual discussions, and learning simulations, is the foundation for creating a positive learning atmosphere. The heads of madrasahs in these two institutions are actively involved in providing support, creating open spaces for conversation, and inspiring teachers.

The research details how madrasah heads at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran have a central role in designing and implementing effective supervision management strategies. The implications of these findings can help similar institutions to formulate more appropriate policies and actions to improve the quality of the learning process. In closing, this research not only creates a deeper understanding of the management of the supervision of the head of the madrasah, but also provides a foundation for innovation and further development in an effort to improve the quality of education in the madrasah.

CONCLUSION

The management of the supervision of the head of the madrasah plays a significant role in improving the quality of the learning process at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran. With a holistic approach, such as group discussions, task delegation, and training, madrasah heads play the role of change agents who nurture and motivate teachers. Training, deliberation, and individual motivation activities become a continuous investment in improving teacher competence.

The initiative of madrasah heads to follow the latest educational trends also has a positive impact on the quality of learning, providing guidance for similar institutions to develop effective supervision management.

Supervision planning for the head of madrasah at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process, is realized through short-term, medium-term, and long-term programs and targets, by forming a Supervision Assistant Team which is given a Decree (SK) by the Head of the madrasah.

The organization of supervision at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung Regency involves various activities, such as group discussions, class visits, individual talks, and learning simulations. Through group discussions, madrasah heads interact with teachers to identify difficulty factors and find solutions to improve the quality of learning. Class visits are carried out to directly observe teacher professionalism and student involvement. Then the head of the madrasah creates a supervision team which is given the task of making supervision goals and making a supervision schedule.

Although there is still a bad feeling between the two parties, the feeling may arise due to differences in teaching experience, age, perception of supervision implementation. The learning simulation involves the demonstration of learning practices by the head of the madrasah, allowing the teacher to conduct introspection and self-improvement. Thus, the implementation of supervision becomes an effective means to ensure the quality of the learning process in the two madrasahs.

Obstacles that occurred at MTs YPP Darul Hikam and MTs Al-Falah Banjaran Bandung in supervising the head of the madrasah to improve the quality of the teaching and learning process, related to teacher discipline, conflicting situations and conditions, inadequate facilities and infrastructure, limited funds, lack of teacher mentality, teachers in the field of study are not the same as their educational background, and the busyness of the head of the madrasah that clashes with the supervision schedule at his school.

Supervision of the Implementation of Teaching and Learning Activities, Group Discussions, Class Visits, Individual Talks, Learning Simulations, Motivating Teachers, Delegation of Supervision Implementation, Discussion, and Delegation of Supervision Implementation. Analysis of the documents showed the existence of teacher professional development programs through training, workshops, and other activities recognized by the Ministry of Religious Affairs.

This supports findings from direct observation in the classroom, which show the application of varied learning methods and the use of technology to support learning. As a result, the quality of the learning process in both madrasahs can be considered adequate and continue to improve through the supervision management efforts of the head of the madrasah.

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